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Original Article

Gaye Atak¹, Fevzi Yılmaz², İnan Beydilli³, Cemil Kavalcı⁴, Bülent Çekiç⁵, Yavuz Fatih Yavuz⁶, Tayfun Anıl Demir⁷

1. MD, Kepez State Hospital, Emergency Department, Antalya/Turkey
2. Prof. University of Health Sciences, Antalya Training and Research Hospital, Emergency Department, Antalya/Turkey
3. Associate Prof. Mersin City Hospital Training and Research Hospital, Emergency Department, Mersin/Turkey
4. Prof. University of Health Sciences, Antalya Training and Research Hospital, Emergency Department, Antalya/Turkey
5. Associate Prof. University of Health Sciences, Antalya Training and Research Hospital, Department of radiology, Antalya/Turkey
6. MD, University of Health Sciences, Antalya Training and Research Hospital, Emergency Department, Antalya/Turkey
7. MD, Antalya Gazipaşa State Hospital, Emergency Department, Antalya/Turkey

Corresponding Authors: Fevzi Yılmaz, MD, Prof., University of Health Sciences, Antalya Training and Research Hospital, Emergency Department, fevzi_yilmaz2002@yahoo.com

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Evaluation of Volume Status And Treatment Response With Point-of-Care Inferior Vena Cava Ultrasound in Patients With Gastrointestinal Bleeding

ABSTRACT

Background: Gastrointestinal bleeding (GIB) is a medical problem with significant morbidity and mortality and high consumption of healthcare resources, and is one of the main reasons for consultation in emergency department (ED). In critically ill patients, measuring the Inferior Vena Cava (IVC) diameter by bedside ultrasonography helps in the evaluation of intravascular status.

Objective: The aim of this study was to assess the association of point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS) used by emergency physicians to examine IVC diameter ratio in patients with GIB.

Methods: A single-center prospective observational study was conducted on consecutive patients with GIB who presented to the ED. Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of the patients, laboratory results and pre- and post-treatment IVC diameter were measured. Patients were divided into two groups as upper GIB (UGIB) and lower GIB (LGIB) based on endoscopic data.

Results: A total of 150 patients were included in our study. 39.3% of the patients were female, 60.7% were male, and the mean age was 59.25 ± 19.91 (min: 19, max: 93). 77% (n=116) of the patients presented with UGIB, and 23% (n=34) with LGIB. In patients with UGIB, IVC MIN and IVC MAX values were significantly increased 2 hours after treatment ($p < 0.05$); IVCCI value after 2 hours was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). In patients with LGIB, IVC MIN, IVC MAX and IVCCI were

statistically insignificant in measurements taken 2 hours after treatment ($p>0.05$). IVC MIN and IVC MAX values of the entire group were significantly increased at the 2-hour measurement after treatment ($p<0.05$), however, IVCCI changes were statistically insignificant ($p>0.05$).

Conclusion: The inferior vena cava diameter ratio was independently associated with a poor outcome in patients with GIB.

Keywords: Inferior vena cava, Gastrointestinal bleeding, Volume Status; Prognosis

Introduction

Acute gastrointestinal bleeding (GIB) is a potentially life-threatening abdominal emergency and remains a common cause of emergency department (ED) visits and hospitalizations (1, 2). Upper GIB (UGIB) is defined as bleeding derived from a source proximal to the ligament of Treitz. The incidence of UGIB is approximately 100 cases per 100,000 population per year (3). Despite advances in diagnosis and treatment in recent years, the mortality rate in GIB varies between 2 and 15% and, there is no decrease in mortality rate (1, 4, 5). Therefore, in patients presenting to the ED with GIB, it is necessary to have effective decision rules to identify low-risk patients who can be safely discharged and to identify high-risk patients who need more invasive management (6).

Invasive and non-invasive methods are used to assess the intravascular volume status of critically ill patients presenting to the ED and to accurately and rapidly determine their response to fluid therapy (7). In clinical practice, non-invasive methods such as mental status changes, skin turgor pressure and skin dryness, capillary refill time, mucous membrane status, extremity temperature, palpation of peripheral pulses, heart rate and blood pressure, orthostatic blood pressure, and physical examination findings such as urine volume, chest radiography, and laboratory parameters and

Invasive methods such as monitoring cardiac output or central venous pressure (CVP) are used (8). Especially in critically ill patients, an invasive method such as central venous catheter insertion is required to determine intravascular volume status and measure CVP (7, 8). Several studies have emphasized that changes in the volume status can be inferred by using point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS). The collapsibility index (CI) of the IVC (IVC CI), which is a ratio of the change in the IVC diameter during the respiratory cycle, currently is being used to estimate the CVP (6, 9).

The use of POCUS as a noninvasive method for hemodynamic monitoring can also guide the clinician in transfusion/resuscitation strategies and identify patients with poor prognosis at an early stage (10). POCUS is a quick, effective, safe, inexpensive, and accurate hemodynamic assessment tool. In recent years, sonographic IVC diameters have been studied in various conditions associated with hypo- and hypervolemia, such as shock, trauma, and heart failure (11). IVC ultrasound is non-invasive and relatively easy to perform, and has been used extensively in the ED. However, there are few studies on sonographic IVC diameters measurements in GIB, where volume status is crucial (6, 11). The purpose of this study was to measurements IVC diameters using POCUS both before and after treatment in patients with acute GIB to determine the patient's fluid status and prognosis.

Methods

This study was conducted prospectively in patients who applied to Health of Sciences University Antalya Training and Research Hospital Department of Emergency Medicine with GIB between 01/11/2017 and 01/11/2018, after obtaining the approval of the Hospital Ethics Committee numbered 2017-232 (Decision No: 19/02).

Patients under 18 years of age, patients with a preliminary diagnosis of invasive gastroenteritis, patients in whom optimal

imaging could not be obtained on ultrasonography due to reasons such as obesity or inability to position, patients diagnosed with GIB at an external center and referred to our hospital, pregnant patients, and patients who did not consent to the study were excluded from the study. The study protocol was developed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Consent was obtained from patients who were conscious and from their families for those with altered consciousness.

In our study, patients who met the specified criteria were examined for age, gender, comorbidities, medication use, presenting symptoms, vital signs (systolic and diastolic blood pressure, pulse, respiratory rate, O₂ saturation), and laboratory results (complete blood count, electrolyte, liver and kidney function tests, coagulation, and blood gas values). Serial sonographic IVC diameter measurements were performed on patients in the inspiratory and expiratory phases pre- and post-treatment. Patients' endoscopy results, Glasgow-Blatchford Score (GBS), medical outcomes (ward admission, intensive care admission, discharge from emergency and exitus) and 30-day mortality rates were calculated. Patients were divided into two groups as upper GIB and lower GIB based on examination findings and endoscopic data.

Inferior Vena Cava Ultrasonography

Ultrasonographic imaging was performed at the bedside by two emergency physicians trained in basic and advanced emergency ultrasonography. IVC diameters were quantified in the long axis from the subcostal view with a 4-MHz phased array US transducer (BC; Mindray, Shenzhen, China). To standardize the measurements, the patients were only examined with US when spontaneously breathing, with the patients in the supine position. The intrahepatic IVC was measured from a site that was 1 to 2 cm distant from the right atrium; the inspiratory change in the IVC diameter was recorded. Similarly, the expiratory IVC diameter was quantified, and

the inferior vena cava collapsibility index (IVCCI) was determined as follows: $[(IVC \text{ size on expiration} - IVC \text{ size on inspiration}) / IVC \text{ size on expiration}] \times 100$. (10).

The abbreviations IVC MIN was used for inspiratory IVC measurements, and IVC MAX was used for expiratory IVC measurements. The abbreviations IVC-1 MIN and IVC-1 MAX were used for inspiratory and expiratory IVC measurements taken at the time of admission, respectively. The abbreviations IVC-2 MIN and IVC-2 MAX were used for inspiratory and expiratory IVC measurements taken at the second hour, respectively.

Statistical Analysis

Study data were analyzed with the SPSS version 22.0 software package for Windows (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY). A normal distribution was determined by Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Mean and standard deviation were used to display data conforming to a parametric distribution; median, minimum, and maximum values were used for data that did not. Categorical variables were represented by the number of cases and percentiles. ANOVA and Student t-tests were used to analyze parametric data with categorical variables; Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to analyze non-parametric data; Pearson chi-square and Fisher exact tests were used to analyze categorical variables with each other; and Pearson correlation tests were used to compare quantitative data. Student t-tests were used to identify the columns that led to significance for parameters identified as significant in the ANOVA test, and Mann-Whitney U tests were used to identify the columns that led to significance in the Kruskal-Wallis test. Data changes over time were analyzed using the paired samples test. A p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Of the 150 patients included in the study, 39.3% were female, 60.7% were male, and the mean age was 59.25 ± 19.91 years (min: 19, max: 93). 77% (n=116) of the patients presented with UGIB, and 23% (n=34) with LGIB. No difference was found between the groups in terms of age, gender and comorbid diseases ($p > 0.05$). Melena and hematemesis were found to be significantly higher in UGIB, while hematochezia was found to be significantly higher in LGIB ($p < 0.05$). 33% of patients were taking regular medications. The most commonly used medication was low molecular weight heparin (LMWH). No difference was found between the groups in terms of predisposing medication use ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1).

In the ultrasonographic measurements taken at admission in patients with UGIB, IVC-1 MIN, IVC-1 MAX and IVCCI-1 were detected as (0.89 ± 0.28 ; 1.59 ± 0.33 ; 0.45 ± 0.1), respectively, While in the measurements taken 2 hours later, IVC-2 MIN, IVC-2 MAX and IVCCI-2 were detected as (0.93 ± 0.29 ; 1.65 ± 0.35 ; 0.44 ± 0.12), respectively. In patients with LGIB, in the measurements taken at the time of admission, IVC-1 MIN, IVC-1 MAX and IVCCI-1 were detected as (0.99 ± 0.29 ; 1.68 ± 0.29 ; 0.42 ± 0.11), respectively, while in the measurements taken 2 hours later, VCI-2 MIN, VCI-2 MAX and IVCCI-2 were detected as (1.02 ± 0.32 ; 1.73 ± 0.31 ; 0.42 ± 0.11), respectively (Table 2).

In patients with UGIB, IVC-2 MIN and IVC-2 MAX values were significantly increased 2 hours after treatment ($p < 0.05$); IVCCI-2 value after 2 hours was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). In patients with LGIB, IVC-2 MIN, IVC-2 MAX and IVCCI-2 were statistically insignificant in measurements taken 2 hours later ($p > 0.05$). IVC MIN and IVC MAX values of the entire group were significantly increased at the 2-hour measurement ($p < 0.05$), however, IVCCI changes were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

According to the endoscopic/colonoscopy results, the most common causes of GI bleeding were duodenal ulcers (42%) (n=63), gastritis (12%) (n=18), and esophageal variceal bleeding (8%) (n=12). No bleeding source was detected In 20 patients (13.3%). According to endoscopy results, the most common ulcer grade in the study group was Forrest 3, at 39.7% (n=25) (Table 4).

The relationship between IVC MIN, IVC MAX, IVCCI levels and patient outcomes is shown in Table 5. IVC-1 MIN and IVCCI-1 levels were significantly lower in patients admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) than in those admitted to the ward ($p < 0.05$). IVC MIN, IVC MAX, and IVCCI levels were significantly lower in patients who Exitus than in those admitted to the ward and ICU ($p < 0.05$) (Table 5).

In patients who died in hospital, the change in IVC-1 MIN, IVC-1 MAX, and IVCCI-1 values after 2 hours was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). However, in patients who died in hospital, IVC-1 MIN and IVC-1 MAX levels were significantly lower, and IVCCI-1 levels were significantly higher compared to patients who survived ($p < 0.05$) (Table 6).

Discussion

In our study, no difference was found between the UGIB and LGIB groups in terms of IVC MIN, IVC MAX, and IVCCI values measured at admission and 2 hours after treatment ($p > 0.05$). However, when comparing the groups within themselves, IVC-2 MIN and IVC-2 MAX values were significantly increased in patients with UGIB after treatment ($p < 0.05$); the change in IVCCI-2 over the 2-hour period was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). In patients with LGIB, changes in IVC-2 MIN, IVC-2 MAX, and IVCCI-2 were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). IVC MIN and IVC MAX values in both groups were significantly increased in the 2-hour post-treatment measurement ($p < 0.05$), however, the changes in IVCCI were statistically

insignificant ($p>0.05$). When examining the relationship between patient outcomes and IVC MIN, IVC MAX, and IVCCI values, IVC-1 MIN and IVCCI-1 levels were found to be significantly lower in patients admitted to the ICU than in those admitted to the ward ($p<0.05$). Furthermore, IVC MIN, IVC MAX, and IVCCI levels in patients who died were found to be significantly lower than in those admitted to the hospital ward and ICU ($p<0.05$). The results of this study indicate that a high IVC diameter ratio in patients with GIB was associated with poor outcomes.

Previous studies have investigated the association between IVC collapsibility or diameter, and the outcomes of critically ill patients with various diseases. However, there are very few studies that measure IVC collapsibility or diameter with POCUS in the management or in determining the prognosis with GIB (12,13). Multiple scoring systems, such as GBS and AIMS65, have been used to determine the prognosis of patients with GIB (14,15). However, these scoring systems have limitations in identifying high-risk patients who may require in-patient endoscopy, embolization, or surgical treatment, or patients at high risk of death (12).

UGIB can lead to significant hemodynamic instability, necessitating rapid and precise decision-making for effective management. The measurement of the IVC diameter, IVCCI using bedside ultrasonography provides information about the intravascular volume (16). In cases of UGIB, where volume loss is a prime concern, a collapsible or small IVC may indicate significant hypovolemia, guiding the need for fluid resuscitation or blood transfusion. Conversely, a dilated IVC with minimal respiratory variation might suggest a different pathophysiological mechanism, such as cardiac dysfunction. Given the complexity and rapid progression of UGIB, integrating these measurements into the initial evaluation can be vital. They not only facilitate a more tailored approach to fluid

and blood product resuscitation but also may aid in the early identification of patients requiring more aggressive interventions, such as endoscopy or surgery (17).

Conclusion

Studies on patients with trauma or septic shock have found a significant relationship between IVC diameter and hypovolemia, blood loss, and in-hospital mortality (18-20). It has also been reported that the IVC diameter ratio is significantly correlated with markers of shock and is a predictor of mortality in patients with trauma and septic shock (21,22). In our study, IVC MIN, IVC MAX, and IVCCI levels of patients who died were found to be significantly lower than those of patients who survived ($p<0.05$).

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Table 1. Comparison of patients with UGIB and LGIB in terms of demographic and clinical characteristics

		UGIB Median (min- max)/n(%)	LGIB Median (min- max)/n(%)	Total Median (min- max)/n(%)	p
Age		63,5 (20-93)	65 (19-88)	64 (19-93)	0,518
Gender	Male	67 (%57,8)	24 (%70,6)	91 (%60,7)	0,178
	Female	49 (%42,2)	10 (%29,4)	59 (%39,3)	
Symptoms	Melena	101 (%87,1)	5 (%14,7)	106 (%70,7)	<0,001
	Hematemesis	51 (%44)	0	51 (%34)	<0,001
	Hematochezia	2 (%1,7)	29 (%85,3)	31 (%20,7)	<0,001
	Syncope	22 (%19)	4 (%11,8)	26 (%17,3)	0,329
	Other	5 (%4,3)	0	5 (%3,3)	0,218
Comorbidities	Total	80 (%69)	24 (%70,6)	104 (%69,3)	0,857
	DM	28 (%24,1)	3 (%8,8)	31 (%20,7)	0,052
	HT	27 (%23,3)	3 (%8,8)	30 (%20)	0,064
	CAD	25 (%21,6)	7 (%20,6)	32 (%21,3)	0,904
	CKD	16 (%13,8)	5 (%14,7)	21 (%14)	>0,999
	AF	4 (%3,4)	1 (%2,9)	5 (%3,3)	>0,999
	CHF	12 (%10,3)	2 (%5,9)	14 (%9,3)	0,737
	Malignancy	7 (%6)	6 (%17,6)	13 (%8,7)	0,075
	CH	4 (%3,4)	1 (%2,9)	5 (%3,3)	>0,999
	CVD	7 (%6)	2 (%5,9)	9 (%6)	>0,999
	CLD	11 (%9,5)	1 (%2,9)	12 (%8)	0,299
	COPD	2 (%1,7)	1 (%2,9)	3 (%2)	0,540
Others	13 (%11,2)	2 (%5,9)	15 (%10)	0,552	
Predisposing Drug Use	Total	34 (%31,8)	11 (%39,3)	45 (%33,3)	0,453
	LMWH	3 (%2,8)	0	3 (%2,2)	>0,999
	Clopidogrel	16 (%15)	5 (%17,9)	21 (%15,6)	0,770
	NOAC (Apiksaban/Dabigatran)	5 (%4,7)	0	5 (%3,7)	0,583
	ASA	13 (%12,1)	5 (%17,9)	18 (%13,3)	0,531
	Vitamin K antagonist	2 (%1,9)	1 (%3,6)	3 (%2,2)	>0,999
	NSAIDs	1 (%0,9)	1 (%3,6)	2 (%1,5)	0,373

*Mann Whitney U Testi, **Pearson Kikare Testi, *** Fisher Exact Test

DM: Diabetes Mellitus, HT: Hypertension, CAD: Coronary Artery Disease, CKD: Chronic Kidney Disease, AF: Atrial Fibrillation, CHF: Congestive heart failure, CH: Chronic Hepatitis, CVD: Cerebrovascular Disease, CLD: Chronic Liver Disease, COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, LMWH: Low-Molecular-Weight Heparin, NOAC: novel oral anticoagulant, ASA: acetylsalicylic acid, NSAIDs: Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

Table 2. IVC MIN, IVC MAX, and IVCCI levels, vital signs, laboratory findings, and GBS In patients with UGIB and LGIB.

	UGIB Median (min- max)/n(%)	LGIB Median (min- max)/n(%)	Total Median (min- max)/n(%)
Pulse	90 (50-145)	92 (58-138)	90 (50-145)
SBP	119,5 (69-196)	123 (87-187)	120 (69-196)
DBP			
SpO2	96 (75-98)	95 (90-99)	95 (75-99)
Hemoglobin	9,45 (3,8-16,4)	10,6 (3,7-14,8)	10 (3,7-16,4)
BUN	29 (5-160)	22 (9-131)	27,5 (5-160)
lactate	1,87 (0,46-6,14)	1,42 (0,46-3,9)	1,7 (0,46-6,14)
INR	1,1 (0,9-8,8)	1,1 (0,8-1,5)	1,1 (0,8-8,8)
IVC-1 MIN	0,91±0,29	0,89±0,28	0,99±0,29
IVC-1 MAX	1,60±0,32	1,59±0,33	1,68±0,29
IVCCI-1	0,44±0,11	0,45±0,1	0,42±0,11
IVC-2 MIN	0,95±0,30	0,93±0,29	1,02±0,32
IVC-2 MAX	1,67±0,34	1,65±0,35	1,73±0,31
IVCCI-2	0,44±0,12	0,44±0,12	0,42±0,11
GBS	7,5 (0-13)	10 (0-17)	9 (0-17)

Fisher exact test, Mann Whitney U Testi, Student t test

*SBP: systolic blood pressure DBP: diastolic blood Pressure SpO2: oxygen saturation

Table 3. IVC MIN, IVC MAX and IVCCI levels in patients with UGIB and LGIB.

	UGIB				LGIB			
	Initial value Mean±SD	last value Mean±SD	Change Mean±SD	p	Initial value Mean±SD	last value Mean±SD	Change Mean±SD	p
IVC-MIN	0,89±0,28	0,93±0,29	- 0,04±0,13	0,001	0,99±0,29	1,02±0,32	- 0,03±0,14	0,278
IVC-MAX	1,59±0,33	1,65±0,35	- 0,07±0,19	<0,001	1,68±0,29	1,73±0,31	- 0,05±0,18	0,140
IVC CI	0,45±0,1	0,44±0,12	0,01±0,07	0,302	0,42±0,11	0,42±0,11	0±0,06	0,737

Paired samples test

Table 4. Patients' Endoscopy and Colonoscopy Results and Distribution According to Forrest Classification

Endoscopy and Colonoscopy Results	n	%
Duodenal ulcer	63	42,0
Gastritis	18	12,0
Hemorrhoids	5	3,3
Arteriovenöz malformasyon	2	1,3
Esophageal varices	12	8,0
Portal gastropathy	2	1,3
Bleeding source not found	20	13,3
Other	21	14
Endoscopy not performed	17	11,3
Endoscopic Classification		
Forrest 1a	3	4,8
Forrest 1b	5	7,9
Forrest 1c	2	3,2
Forrest 2a	12	19,0
Forrest 2b	16	25,4
Forrest 3	25	39,7

Table 5. Relationship between patient outcomes and IVC MIN, IVC MAX, and IVCCI levels

	Yatış yeri			p
	Ward Mean±SD	ICU Mean±SD	Exitus Mean±SD	
IVC-1 MIN	0,97±0,28	0,79±0,23	0,38±0,06	<0,001ABC
IVC-1 MAX	1,62±0,32	1,6±0,32	1,09±0,02	0,018BC
IVCCI-1	0,41±0,09	0,51±0,1	0,65±0,06	<0,001ABC
IVC-2 MIN	1,03±0,28	0,77±0,22	0,42±0,05	<0,001AB
IVC-2 MAX	1,69±0,33	1,65±0,35	1,10±0,03	0,009BC
IVCCI-2	0,39±0,1	0,53±0,09	0,61±0,05	<0,001AB

Anova Test A: P<0.05 for Ward /ICU; B: P<0.05 for Ward/Exitus C: P<0.05 for ICU/Exitus

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